

IMPREGNATION OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES MANUFACTURED BY DOUBLE BELT PRESS TECHNIQUE

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SUMMARY: The manufacturing of thermoplastic composites by continuously running double belt press has become one of the most effective techniques for high quantity production. The combination of thermoplastic materials and fabric layers during the manufacturing implies impregnation phenomena of the fabric layers distinct from one in RTM that has been frequently discussed in many previous papers. Here, the work is focused on the clarification of the impregnation phenomenon which occurred in the continuous manufacturing process. Results were presented by the observation of samples that were fabricated at different process velocity to determine the impregnation time. Meanwhile, further analysis and experiments revealed that variation of mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites could be realized by using different process velocity and temperature boundary conditions to change the impregnation degree of the reinforcing fabrics.

KEYWORDS: thermoplastic composites, manufacturing science, impregnation, double belt press

INTRODUCTION

A timesaving manufacturing process to produce composites with expected performance and as low cost as possible is always a subject to be pursued by industries. The fabrication of thermoplastic composites by means of a continuously running double belt press is one of the most effective manufacturing methods for high quantity production. During the process, thermoplastic materials will melt and then penetrate into the fabric layers under pressure applied by the double belts. It is evident that the penetration process of the thermoplastic flow into fabric layers is directly relevant to the impregnation of the fabrics which have dominant effects on mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites if the fabrics and matrix has been determined.

As known, the impregnation of fabrics as reinforcement in thermoset composites has become one of the focused problems since resin transfer molding (RTM), one of favorite methods to fabricate structural composite, is basically a process of preform mould filling with liquid resins. Analysis on the impregnation was set up on the basis of Darcy's theory [1, 2] which has been introduced to analyze mass and energy transfer in porous materials [3], and it concluded the complicated relation between seepage velocity and pressure drop in fabrics into a parameter — permeability [4, 5, 6, 7, 8].

It is certain that the supposition and application of the permeability lead to simplification of analysis and scaling of fabric impregnation process. But it is necessary to point out that the

permeability described in the Darcy's theory only indicates an overall ability of resins penetrating into porous preform in macro-scale during the RTM process. Thus the theory can be applied only when dimensions of pores and reinforcements are many orders of magnitude less than one in the flow direction. On such basis, the permeability can be determined by experiments [9, 10, 11, 12].

In the continuous manufacturing processing the double belt press, the impregnation of fabrics is developed along the direction of thickness rather than in plane usually in RTM. Thus the dimension in flow direction is comparable with the diameter of the roving constituting fabric layers. As a result, the impregnation of the fabric layers is estimated to be considerably distinct from impregnation phenomena in RTM.

This paper was devoted to clarify the impregnation phenomenon of composite sheets manufactured by using the double belt press with the aid of observation of samples fabricated under the same pressure and temperature boundary conditions in different process period or velocity. Meanwhile, it is also intended that the different degree of impregnation of the fabrics was obtained by applying appropriate process conditions to alter mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites.

OBSERVATION OF THE IMPREGNATION PROCESS

The utilization of the double belt press technique is actually a process of combining fabrics and thermoplastic materials along with the penetration of the molten thermoplastic materials into the fabric layers by pressure. As shown in Fig.1, the thermoplastic materials are processed by heat transfer and conduction originated from heating and cooling plates under pressure produced by a hydraulic system and imposed on the continuous laminates by steel belts. The resident time of the polymer in the high temperature and heating zone will directly have an impact on the molten polymer percolating into the fabric layers. The impregnation process will finally be completed in this zones.

It is no doubt that the completion of the impregnation process should take some time. As a consequence, the abasement or extension of the process period will lead to the decrease or increase of the impregnation degree of fabrics before the impregnation falls into saturation. By using an experimental layup as depicted in Fig.2, the completion of impregnation process could be approximately simulated by the impregnation states of samples produced by the different process period. To control the process period, it is a simple way to apply different process velocity in the manufacturing process.

Fig.1 Manufacturing using the double belt press

Fig.2 Experimental layout of polymer films and fabrics for samples

On the basis of the same pressure and temperature boundary conditions in the four zones depicted in Fig.1, two kinds of samples (1) and (2) with two and four glass fabric layers, shown as in Fig.2, are fabricated at the process velocity of 1.7, 1.3, 0.9, 0.5 and 0.2m/min. Different from common alternative layout, two or four layers of polyamide films are all mounted on the upper surface of the glass fabrics to increase the penetration distance of the molten polyamide. The fabricated samples are then cut into pieces and fixed in epoxy for optical microscope analysis.

As shown in Fig.3, (a)-(c) are pictures of cross sections of the sample (1) produced at the process velocity of 1.7, 0.9 and 0.2 m/min respectively. The ellipses embracing many fibres are cross sections of rovings, where the local white areas inside and outside the rovings are filled by epoxy and indicate fibres not being impregnated. It can be found that, in Fig3-(a), due to the limit resident time to stay in molten state, the polyamide flow infiltrate almost only into the second fabric layer, whereas the fibers inside the rovings of the layer were almost unimpregnated. After that, polyamide filled the whole fabric structure, and fibres inside the rovings lying at the upper layers were gradually partially impregnated at the same time, as shown in Fig.3-(b). This phenomenon may ascribe to the large difference in permeability between the fabrics structures and the fiber bundles. The impregnation process is ultimately

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completed with the full fill of all space outside and inside the rovings as displayed in Fig.3-(c).

A more detailed impregnation process is described in Fig.4. The investigated samples were produced with the experimental layout as described in Fig.2-(2) at a process velocity of 1.7, 1.3, 0.9, 0.5 and 0.2 m/min respectively. It may be discovered that the polyamide first infiltrated the space outside the roving as shown in Fig.4-(a). After that, it began to penetrate into the roving as illustrated in Fig.4-(b), later gradually spread over the roving (see Fig.4-(c,d)) and finally impregnated all fibres in the roving as depicted in Fig.4-(e). Obviously, the white region filled with epoxy became smaller and smaller inside the rovings, thus it manifested that the samples had the impregnation degree increased. Simultaneously, the thickness of thermoplastic sheets became thinner and thinner during the process because the polyamide imposed on the top, as shown in the pictures, gradually penetrated into the roving, impregnated the fibres and squeezed out air at the same time.

The complete impregnation process illustrated above exhibits the strong inhomogeneity of flow pattern in the fabric layers. As described, macro-flow frequently described in the percolation of polymer and impregnation of fabrics in RTM has already lost its meaning since the completion of the impregnation process is not marked by the infiltration of flow through the fabric layers, but determined by the time required to penetrate into the roving. In this regard, the use of permeability given in Darcy's theory to describe an ability of polymer penetrating into the fabrics is inappropriate, and thus the impregnation process through the thickness of the fabrics cannot be predicted by Darcy's theory any more.

It may be concluded that the relative small distance along the infiltration direction of flow extremely magnified the influence of the micro-flow during the impregnation of fabrics, and the micro-flow into the rovings has a dominant effect on the actual impregnation of the fabrics. Such a strong effect of micro-flow on the impregnation is essentially different from one in RTM. Therefore, the description of the impregnation should also be distinct from one in RTM, where macro-flow prevails during the impregnation process and Darcy's theory could consequently be used.

One should pay attention to a case where the micro-flow will gradually lose its dominant position with the increase in thickness of fabric layers. As shown in Fig.3-(b), partial fibres in the rovings of the first and second layer had been impregnated to a different degree when the polyamide reached the bottom of the fabrics. It is logical to think that the micro-flow and inhomogeneous impregnation along the direction of thickness of the fabrics will be too small to have influence on the global flow and impregnation when the thickness is large enough, and the impregnation process will be as same as one in RTM.

Finally, it is emphasized that the special impregnation phenomena in the manufacturing of thermoplastic composites by using a double belt press may give an advantage in obtaining the thermoplastic composites with different impregnation degree by the control of process velocity.

EFFECTS OF IMPREGNATION ON MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

To some extent, the impregnation degree shows a degree of combination between polymer matrix and reinforcements, and must have a deep influence on mechanical properties of composites. As a consequence, variation of mechanical properties of thermoplastic

composites may come true by means of the manufacturing process design of composites featured with different degree of impregnation.

As discussed in the preceding sections, the process velocity in the manufacturing process has a conclusive effect on the impregnation degree of fabrics in thermoplastic composites. Additionally, it can also be easily understood that temperature boundary conditions are also related to the impregnation degree.

By choosing process velocity V_0 , $2V_0$, $3V_0$ and $4V_0$, where V_0 is a reference process velocity, and different process temperature, differently impregnated samples were fabricated by alternately stacking glass fiber fabrics and polyamide films. Their flexural mechanical property was then examined by using a three-point bending test to investigate the effect of impregnation on the mechanical property.

As shown in Fig.5-(a), the relationship between stress (load/area of cross section) and transverse displacement at the loaded point of a beam was obtained from the tests. It is obvious that the samples fabricated at a lower process velocity and thus a longer resident time in the high temperature zone exhibited brittle failure whereas the samples produced at a higher process velocity presented ductile fracture, where the step damage might be seen clearly for the samples at higher process velocity. Meanwhile, as displayed in Fig.6, the flexural modulus and strength was reduced with the increase of process velocity, while the deformation endurance was considerably enhanced for the relative high process velocity. Additionally, a character similar to plastic flow of metal — ductility was first achieved by increasing the process velocity from V_0 to $2V_0$ (see Fig.5-a) even if the deformation endurance held almost unchanged. The similar case could be also observed by decreasing the process temperature from $1.3077T_0$ to $1.0769T_0$ at a process velocity as shown in Fig.5-(b), where T_0 is a reference temperature.

Fig.5 Flexural behavior of samples fabricated at different process velocity and temperature

It is necessary to understand that all phenomena observed in Fig.5 and Fig.6 were results mostly in response to the variation of impregnation no mater what parameters such as process velocity , temperature boundary conditions or others in the manufacturing process are employed to change mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites. Evidently, controlling impregnation would be a way to vary mechanical properties and optimize the manufacturing process of thermoplastic composites by using continuously running a double belt press.

Fig.6 Flexural strength and deformation endurance of samples

CONCLUSION

Results from experiments showed that melted polymer promptly penetrated the fabric layers during the manufacturing process. The high resistance to the polymer flow into the roving produced strong inhomogeneity of flow pattern in fabric layers and considerably delayed the impregnation inside the rovings. Therefore, polymer first filled the space outside the rovings before fibres inside were gradually impregnated. On the other hand, thermoplastic composites with different degree of impregnation could be obtained by appropriately controlling the impregnation process resulting from the design of process velocity as well as temperature boundary conditions in the manufacturing process. Then mechanical properties of thermoplastic composites could be varied.

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